

The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Music Recommendation: A Reproducibility Study: A Reproducibility Study

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Abstract

This report is a reproducibility study of the work of D. Kowald et al. regarding the popularity bias in music recommendation systems [KSL19]. This report follows the whole data science pipeline presented in the original paper in order to identify steps in this process with missing or unclear information. While some steps were not transparently documented, the main hypothesis of the work was again confirmed using different subsets of the original full data set.

1 Introduction

In this paper we want to examine the results presented by D. Kowald et al. in [KSL19]. The paper builds upon another work from Abdollahpouri et al. in [AMBM19] and examines the effects of the popularity bias in state-of-the-art recommender systems from a users perspective. More specifically, how the recommended items differs from the expectations of different user groups. While in the paper by Abdollahpouri et al. the movie domain was chosen, the new paper by [KSL19] focuses on the domain of music recommendations. In order to investigate this topic, D. Kowald et al. proposes two main research questions, namely:

- *RQ1*: To what extent are users or groups of users interested in popular artists?
- *RQ2*: To what extent does the popularity bias of recommendation algorithms affect users with different inclination to mainstream music

We now want to reproduce the results given in the paper, starting from the original data set by [Sch16], to see whether all information given in the paper is sufficient to do so. Additionally, we want to test if slight changes to the presented procedure, or uncertainties in the methodology description, might influence the validity of the outcomes. The value of this reproducibility study lies in gaining deeper insights into the methods of the original paper that can then be used as an additional point of reference for further research.

2 Reproducibility of results

In the following chapter we now want to further analyze the data science pipeline used in [KSL19], whether or not we can reproduce the findings presented, if changes in the individual steps influence the outcome and if so, to what extend. The authors of the study supplied links to their original notebook used for the creation of the plots, as well as to the full data set and their already preprocessed subsets derived from the full data set. Using the notebook and the preprocessed data subsets, we were able to execute them in various environments using different version of Python 3 and achieved the same plots and significance test results as are presented in the paper. After now being able to reproduce the results through means of rerunning their supplied project, we now take a closer look at the individual steps and decisions made in the process, as well as the steps needed to recreate the preprocessed input data from the original full data set. For this we create our own experiment setup and analyse whether changes to the proposed pipeline or uncertainties in the methodology description a) influence the outcome and b) lead to a result that is not anymore in line with the findings of the original paper.

Figure 1: Histograms comparing the distribution of the different data samples

2.1 Experiment set up

To reproduce the result presented in the original paper, we want to stay as close to the original experiment setup as possible. The software tools used and described in the original paper are the following: Python 3, Jupyter, as well as the python packages `Pandas`, `Matplotlib`, `Surprise`, `Numpy`, `Scipy`, `Sklearn`. No specific IDE or OS was defined. To now emulate the test setup in the original paper, we used the collaborative programming environment Deepnote, running Python 3.7 and Jupyter. Additionally, all the python packages described above were used in their current versions. Due to the large size of the LFM-1b data set, the initial splitting of the data was done locally on an M1-Mac running macOS Monterey 12.01 and Python 3.9. Used Source Code can be retrieved from XXX [?]

2.2 Data selection

For their analysis, the original paper chose the freely available LFM-1b data set [Sch16] containing over 120.000 Last.fm users with a combined number of 1.1 billion listening events. In order to receive a more manageable data set, the user base was split into three groups, based on their mainstreamness score. This metric describes how "mainstream" the listening habit of an individual user is. Using this score as a reference, the user base for the analysis was according to the original paper split into three parts, each containing 1000 users: 1000 users with the lowest mainstreamness score, 1000 with the highest, and 1000 around the median [KSL19]. Since the full data set provides several mainstreamness metrics, the global score `mainstreamness_global` was chosen since it matches with the column names given in the provided sub-files. After further inspection, the methods for splitting in the paper is not matching the results of the reproduction, as can be seen in Figure ?? on the left.

In order to achieve a user distribution closer to the one used in the paper, two different alternative approaches are explored, which are based in part on the paper by Abdollahpouri et al. which was used as the basis for our analyzed paper. In their paper, Abdollahpouri et al. split the data into the lowest 20% of the mainstreamness score, the highest 20%, and the grouped the rest together as the middle. Because of this, we want to explore also using the different quantiles for our data sampling. More specifically, we want to either:

- ...randomly sample 1000 users from the highest and lowest 20%. as well as 1000 users around the median (from now on *Q20 Q80 1k*)
- ... or randomly sample 600 users from the highest and lowest 20% and the others from the remaining user pool between Q20 and Q80, in order to more accurately preserve the original user distributions (*Q20 Q80*)

The results of this process can be seen in the histogram in Figure ?? on the right. Comparing the individual results, it can be assumed that some sort of leveling algorithm was applied to the Top/Bottom 1k sampled data set, since the peaks in the original data set align with the peaks of the Top/Bottom 1k sampling, but the edges around the peaks are more populated. We now want to further investigate if the described changes in the sampling might influence the validity

of the results. To do this, we want to proceed with two sampling methods, the Top/Bottom 1k sampling as is described in the original paper, and our adapted random sampling using the lowest and highest 20% to sample 600 users each, and the remaining 60% in the middle to randomly sample 1800 additional users.

2.3 Data preparation

For the data preparation we again aim to follow the described steps of the original paper, as well as the provided source code closely. For additional transparency we want to detail some of the conducted pre-processing steps in this chapter – at times also in a critical light.

The `user_events.txt` file that is used as the primary source of information for the recommender system contains a data set with the following attributes: user, artist, album, track and timestamp. Information about whether a given song was listened to its end (or just a portion of it) is not provided. Giving weights based on it could lead to a different result - which would not be necessarily better. The table is aggregated (as part of the data preparation): the user and the artist attributes are kept, and the third column contains the number of occurrences (count). Here some information is lost, as we (and neither the algorithm) do not know anymore whether a given user likes many of the songs of the given artist, or just favours one or a few of their songs very much. This information however could be important, as there are artists who have songs from quite different genres, or changes their music style to a more popular "mainstream" one from one album to another. To further pre-process the data and make it ready for usage in the algorithms, the preferences of the users for artists are scaled to a value between 1 and 1000 using the `MinMaxScaler()`, which belongs to the `sklearn.preprocessing` package. Afterwards, the data is randomly split in train (80%) and test data (20%) by the `train_test_split()` function which belongs to the `sklearn.model_selection` package. No cross validation or repeated random splits were applied. The seed (the random state) was provided in their code and set to 0. No further conditions are provided, meaning the ratio of the mainstreamness groups LowMS, MedMS, HighMS is not preserved in the resulting sets. Furthermore, the proportions of the users are not preserved either, meaning some users possibly appear more often compared to their occurrence on the original table in the test set than others. Additionally it should be noted that since the scaling was done before the test/train split, some information is leaking from the test set into the training set for the models. This fact was also not changed during our reproduction of the results in order to keep the number of independent variables that might influence the results focused on the different sampling methods. Handling missing values was not necessary, there was not any missing value.

2.4 Model building

The models are trained using six different algorithms. The first two algorithms (Random and Most-Popular) can rather be considered as references, while the other four algorithms are implemented in the python package *surprise*.

- Random - Suggests a set of random artists (that were not already listened to by the given user based on the train set).
- MostPopular - Suggests the most popular artists (that are not already listened to by the given user based on the train set).
- UserItemAvg - Implements the `BaselineOnly()` function: the baseline estimation of a rating is calculated as follows:

$$b_{ui} = ac + b_u + b_i$$

where 'ac' is the average value of the 'count' columns, while b_u and b_i indicate the observed deviations of user u and item i , respectively, from the average. To receive these variables, the following least squares problem is solved:

$$\sum_{(u,i) \in K} (r_{ui} - ac - b_u - b_i)^2 + \lambda (\sum_u b_u^2 + \sum_i b_i^2)$$

Which contains a regularizing term weighted by λ . (r_{ui} is the actual count of the given artist of the given user.) [Kor10]

- UserKNN - Applies the `KNNBasic()` function from the *surprise* package, with $k = 40$. The recommendations are based on the given users closest 40 neighbours.

	UserItemAvg	UserKNN	UserKNNAvg	NMF
LowMS	42.948	49.76	46.5809	38.4223
MedMS	33.9001	42.4837	37.5854	30.5963
HighMS	40.6864	45.991	43.2426	37.2851
All	38.5612	45.6321	41.8842	34.8799
p-value Low-High	1.45746e-10	1.58651e-24	1.43773e-20	0.00491113
p-value Low-Med	4.0412e-189	4.68088e-114	1.22429e-179	5.52241e-112
p-value Med-High	3.10363e-116	2.56468e-30	2.33948e-78	9.34399e-87

Table 1: Evaluation of Prediction MAE on the original dataset

	UserItemAvg	UserKNN	UserKNNAvg	NMF
LowMS	132.245	128.043	136.733	128.444
MedMS	46.2746	46.5209	47.6433	41.045
HighMS	19.645	26.3795	21.54	16.7073
All	24.5473	30.2966	26.4065	21.2997

Table 2: Evaluation of Prediction MAE on the Top/Bottom 1k dataset

- UserKNNAvg - Combination of the previous two algorithms.
- NMF - Non-negative matrix factorization. The factor is set to 15.

2.5 Model evaluation

The predictions of the recommender systems are evaluated using the test data. For each fitted model, predictions are generated and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is calculated. Additionally the test data is split according to the defined user groups, and the MAE for each group is calculated. Without popularity bias we would expect a model to predict with similar MAE for all user groups. On the other hand a biased model would predict more popular items to all groups and have therefore produce a significantly higher MAE for the *LowMS* then for the *HighMS* user group.

Whether the difference in MAE for different groups is significant is determined using a t-test. The performed t-test is a two-sided test for the null hypothesis that two test samples of calculated MAE values have an identical mean. The null hypothesis is rejected when p is less then 0.05. Table 1 shows the MAE for each model and user group. The table closely reassembles the finding of [KSL19] although with slightly different numbers after the first decimal point. Not only was the *NMF* model the only one which performed better then our baseline algorithm *UserItemAvg* but also was the most fair because it predicts a similar MAE for all groups.

We also included the t-statistics p values for testing if the MAE is different between each group. All calculated p-values are below 0.05 so they are significantly different. Additionally we evaluated the model using our selected data. Table 2 and 3 show the results for the Top/Bottom 1k and the Q20/Q80 sampling respectively.

Since our sampled data sets differ, also the evaluation results show different MAE. None of the models show an improvement from the baseline algorithm (*UserItemAvg*) in respect to overall MAE but also the differences between the groups MAE. To show how significant the difference is we used the same t-test as before to compare the computed MAE values between the LowMS group of the original dataset and the LowMS group from our data selection.

Additionally the GAP score for our prediction results was calculated in accordance to the original paper by D. Kowald et al. in [KSL19]. The results can be seen in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The most similarities with the originally used data split for the GAP score can be seen between the original and the Q20/Q80 split, while the results for the Top/Bottom 1k split is especially skewed for the LowMS group.

	UserItemAvg	UserKNN	UserKNNAvg	NMF
LowMS	72.5503	74.6599	75.3948	71.1272
MedMS	43.65	52.4949	47.6802	40.0756
HighMS	28.8017	43.788	33.7327	25.6024
All	39.0320	50.1223	43.3789	35.7595

Table 3: Evaluation of Prediction MAE on the randomly sampled Q20/Q80 dataset

Figure 2: Original results

Figure 3: Our results using different sampling methods

3 Discussion of findings

The results presented above show quite prominently, that some information regarding the methods to attain the data subset are missing. Nonetheless, while comparing it to different sampling methods, the points made in the original paper still hold and are in some cases even more pronounced. Some points can be made regarding the splitting of the data after the scaling, and thus heaving some data leakage from the test set into the train set. But after showing that the results can be reproduced even with a significantly different split of the data, it can be reasonable to assume that this leakage would not affect the final conclusion of the paper.

4 Conclusion

The original work covers a very interesting and complex topic. Additionally, the approach to cover the problem from a user perspective is a welcome addition to existing scientific discussion. Further papers could additionally also include some of the following aspects that came up during our discussion of the topic:

The better a recommender system is, the more matching items it suggests to users. Instead of relying on the past listening history of the user when evaluating the unfairness of the recommender system, an alternative approach from a user perspective is to collect data about how often users save, like or give high ratings to items that are recommended for them, or when it comes to songs, how often do they listen to it.

In the data sets that are used for this paper the only information about the songs we have is that which users listened to them and when, so indirectly, how often they were listened to by different users. Based on it, it is a hard task to implement an algorithm which would not be biased towards popular songs (or artists in this case). An alternative way to implement a non-biased algorithm would be to use data sets based on complex feature extraction of the songs, so that we receive more information about the songs themselves, about their characteristics (rhythm, tones, bass etc.). Thus, preferred features could be associated to users, and the songs would be recommended to them based on these features instead of other user’s playing history.

References

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